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A STUDY OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN APSPDCL

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ABSTRACT:

One of the most important institutions of the modern world is the industrial organizations, where a large number of people work together for attainment of the organizational objectives through production of goods and services. People are central to the organizational process and therefore, the challenge of new millennium manifests most critically in the area of Human Resource Management. Human Resource Management is one of the most important managerial functions encompassing in its ambit all aspects of the organizational interactions with people, whether within itself or the society around. The electricity industry occupies a unique place in our country. The electricity industry being labor-intensive is a major contribution to the country's economy with its vast potential for creation of employment opportunities in industrial sectors. Business organizations are made up of people and function through people. Electricity industry is no exception this. Hence, it is essential for every organization to adopt human resource management practices in the administration. This paper also analyzes the human resource management in electricity industry.

KEY WORDS : Human resource management, organizations, electricity industry, HRM Practices.

Human resources are assuming increasing significance in modern organizations as, obviously majority of the problems in organizational settings are human and social rather than physical, technical and economic. The failure to recognize this fact causes immense loss to the nation, enterprise and the individual. Human resource development is a pre condition for modern economic growth. Manpower is essential in every country including countries- the set up of capital equipment alone cannot accomplish everything and a certain amount of human capital is necessary for the successful use of physical capital. In a developing economy like India where manpower is available in abundance to meet any conceivable increase in labour demand the real policy problem in efficient use of this untapped vast reservoir of energy.

Power today is one of the top priorities of the nation. It has generally been seen that while planning for capacity additions and preparing feasibility reports and detailed projects reports, all related inputs such as coal linkage, financial resources and related technology inputs etc., are very well tied up. But when it comes to the question of planning for the human resources, generally qualitative statements with very broad and general quantitative presentations, in a few paragraphs are considered sufficient for the purpose of project reports, no care is taken to quantify human resource requirements into various categories, types of skill, degree of experience etc. The present study is an attempt to analyze the human resource management in APSPDCL in prakasam district.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The present study has been taken up in the Andhra Pradesh Southern Power Distribution Company Limited (APSPDCL). Studies on organizational as well as HRD Climate in the power sector are rare and few studies have been conducted so far. Studies of their kind certainly rekindle enthusiasm and spirit of the employees working in the sample divisions in Prakasam

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District as the suggestive measures forwarded by the researcher certainly assist the respective divisions and management of the APSPDCL to take pragmatic decision in employees forever.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The following are the main objectives of the present study:

- To analyze the opinion of employees about training methods in sample divisions.
- To analyze the opinion of employees about salary in sample divisions.
- To offer suitable suggestions to the management of APSPDCL based on the findings of the study.

METHODOLOGY

The study is empirical in nature and based on survey method. The entire data required for the study were collected in 2 stages. The primary data relating to the study have been collected by interviewing the employees with the help of an interview schedule. The secondary data relating to the study have been collected from various published and unpublished records, reports, journals, magazines.

SIZE OF THE SAMPLE

In the first stage, out of 6 APSPDCL divisions operating in Prakasam District two divisions constituting 35 per cent have been selected for the study. Further, out of a total employees of Operating and Maintenance Staff of 372 about 130 accounting for 35 per cent have been chosen as sample. Similarly, in Markapur division, out of total Operating and Maintenance Staff of 302, about 105 accounting for 35 per cent have been chosen as the sample. The simple random sampling technique has been employed to select the sample respondents.

PERIOD OF THE STUDY

The primary data from the sample respondents have been collected during October-December 2013.

FRAMEWORK OF ANALYSIS

For the purpose of analysis of the data, tools like percentage analysis, weighted average method, mean score, and chi-square test have been used.

SOCIO- ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF SAMPLE EMPLOYEES

The socio economic characteristics of the sample respondents may influence the workers in their work place. Therefore, various socio economic characteristics of the workers such as age, education, marital status, income and experience are discussed.

TABLE-1: AGE WISE DISTRIBUTION OF THE RESPONDENTS IN APSPDCL

(Figures in Numbers)

S.No	Age Frequency	Ongole division		Markapur division	
		No. of respondents	% to Total	No. of respondents	% to total
1	25-35	38	29.23	29	27.63
2	35-45	80	61.54	60	57.14
3	45-55	9	6.92	6	5.71
4	55 above	3	2.31	10	9.52
Total		130	100	105	100

Source: survey

Age plays an important role in the attitude of workers in their personal aspects. The age of sample respondents have been classified into 4 groups. Table 1 shows the age-wise classification of sample respondents. As can be seen from the table that out of the total respondents in Ongole division of APSPDCL a majority of 61.54 per cent are in the age group of 35-45 years as against to 57.14 per cent of the Markapur division. It is followed by 29.23 per cent as against to 27.63 per cent in the respective divisions in the age group of 25-35 years.

TABLE-2: EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATIONS OF RESPONDENTS

(Figures in Numbers)

S.No	Choice of Response	Ongole division		Markapur division	
		No. of respondents	% to Total	No. of respondents	% to Total
1	Professional	32	24.62	42	40
2	Technical	98	75.38	63	60
Total		130	100	105	100

Source: survey

Education is one of the important factors that influence the workers' attitude in the work place. The sample respondents are classified into, professional and technical level education. Table 2 shows the education-wise classification of the respondents.

It can be observed from the data that majority 75.38 per cent in Ongole division as against to 60 per cent in Markapur division are technically qualified. Against the above, it can be further observed that 40 per cent of those in Markapur division as against 24.62 per cent of those Ongole division are professional's qualified.

TABLE-3: YEARS OF EXPERIENCE OF THE RESPONDENTS

(Figures in Numbers)

S.No	Years of Experience	Ongole Division		Markapur Division	
		No. of respondents	% to Total	No. of respondents	% to Total
1	Below 5	5	3.85	12	11.43
2	5-10 years	25	19.23	18	17.14
3	10-15 years	40	30.77	30	28.57
4	15 above	60	46.15	45	42.86
Total		130	100	105	100

Source: survey

Experience of employees is measured on the basis of the number of years they have been engaged in this job. Table 3 shows the classification of respondents on the basis of their years of experience.

As evident from the table, out of total respondents in Ongole division, a larger proportion of 46.15 per cent with an experience of above 15 years service in Ongole division against 42.86 per cent in Markapur division. It is followed by 30.77 per cent of Ongole division against 28.57 per cent in Markapur division who are with an experience of 10-15 years.

TABLE- 4: MARITAL STATUS OF THE RESPONDENTS

(Figures in Numbers)

S.No	Choice of Response	Ongole Division		Markapur Division	
		No. of respondents	% to total	No. of respondents	% to total
1	Married	125	96.15	90	85.71
2	Unmarried	5	3.85	15	14.29
Total		130	100	105	100

Source: survey

Job roles and family roles have a bearing on the job performance of the employee. Moreover, emotional intelligence, stability, life style, pattern of expenditure of employees differs from married to unmarried.

Table 4 presents data about marital status of respondents. It is evident from the table that out of total respondents of Ongole division 92.15 per cent as compared to 85.71 per cent of Markapur division are married against lower proportion of them in both the divisions who are unmarried.

TRAINING

TABLE-5: TYPE OF TRAINING PROGRAMMES PREFERRED

(Figures in Numbers)

S. No	Choice of Response	Ongole Division		Markapur Division	
		No. of respondents	%to Total	No. of respondents	%to Total
1	In Service training-on the Job	109	83.85	100	95.24
2	By outside training institute	21	16.15	5	4.76
Total		130	100	105	100

Source: survey

Training of any kind should have its objective of improving the behaviour of employees. So the performance of training becomes more useful. Table 5 explains the opinion of employee about training methods.

It is clearly evident that 95.24 per cent of Operating staff of Markapur division prefers in-service training on the job as compared to 83.85 per cent of those in Ongole division. Compared to 16.15 per cent of operating staff of Ongole division who preferred Training by outside Institute, 4.76 per cent of Markapur division prefer training by the outside Professional Agency.

TABLE-6: THE TRAINING FOCUS AREAS SIGNIFICANT TO PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT IN FUTURE

(Figures in Numbers)

S.No	Focus prospective Training areas	Ongole Division		Markapur Division	
		No. of respondents	%to Total	No. of respondents	%to Total
1	Management Development	27	20.77	37	35.24
2	Computer Software	70	53.84	49	46.67
3	Leadership	30	23.08	12	11.43
4	Time management	3	2.31	7	6.66
Total		130	100	105	100

Source: survey

Leadership is the art of influencing people so that they will strive willingly and enthusiastically towards the achievement of group goals. They would provide the means for the accumulation and transmission of the necessary information to managers for taking decisions.

It is evident that about 53.84 per cent of Ongole division cited computer software training as the prime area for personal development as compared to 46.67 per cent of Markapur division. Further, 23.08 per cent of Ongole division opined leadership as the important area of training focus to personal development.

TABLE-7: EXPECTATIONS FOR ADVANCEMENT IN THE ORGANIZATION

(Figures in Numbers)

S.No	Choice of Response	Ongole division		Markapur Division	
		No. of respondents	%to Total	No. of respondent	%to Total
1	Congenial work environment	25	19.23	24	22.86
2	Quick promotions	56	43.08	50	47.62
3	Promotions of team work	30	23.08	14	13.33
4	Provision of training facility	15	11.54	8	7.62
5	Other	4	3.07	9	8.57
	Total	130	100	105	100

Source: survey

The advancement of an employee from one job position to another job position that has a higher salary range, a higher level Job title, and, often, more and higher level job responsibilities is called a promotion.

It is evident that followed by 22.86 percent of Engineers and Operation and Maintenance Staff of Markapur division expecting congenial work environment for advancement in the organization against 19.23 percent of Ongole division, and 47.62 percent of Markapur division expecting quick promotions against 43.03 percent of Ongole division.

TABLE-8: TRAINING FOR NEW EMPLOYEES

(Figures in Numbers)

S.No	methods	Ongole Division		Markapur Division	
		No. of respondents	%to Total	No. of respondents	%to Total
1	Required for new employees	97	74.62	87	82.86
2	Not required for new employees	33	25.38	18	17.14
	Total	130	100	105	100

Source: survey

Training is necessary both for new and existing employees. Table 8 shows that opinion of employees regarding whether or not training is needed for new employees.

Table 8 shows that 82.86 per cent of employees of Markapur division state that training is required for new employees compared to 74.62 per cent of Ongole division. And 25.38 per cent of employees belonging to Ongole division state that training is not required for new employees compared to 17.14 per cent of Markapur division.

SALARY

TABLE-9: SATISFACTION OF EMPLOYEES AT PRESENT LEVEL OF SALARY

(Figures in numbers)

S.No	methods	Ongole Division		Markapur Division	
		No. of respondents	%to Total	No. of respondents	%to Total
1	satisfied	100	76.92	90	85.71
2	Not satisfied	30	23.08	15	14.29
Total		130	100	105	100

Source: survey

Table 9 shows the satisfaction of employees about their present level of salary. It reveals that among the total respondents, 76.92 per cent are satisfied with their present salary level, while 23.08 per cent are not satisfied with their existing salary level.

TABLE – 10: INCENTIVE SCHEME MOTIVATES THE EMPLOYEE TO WORK MORE

(Figures in Numbers)

S.No	Response	Ongole Division		Markapur Division	
		No. of respondents	%to Total	No. of respondents	%to Total
1	Yes	60	46.15	65	61.91
2	No	70	53.85	40	38.09
3	Total	130	100	105	100

Source: survey

Incentives schemes make a substantial contribution to the raising of productivity, lower costs of production and provide increased earnings for the workers.

As evident from the table10, 61.91 per cent of Operating staff of Markapur division expressed that the incentive system motivates them compared to 46.15 per cent of Ongole division.

CONCLUSION

1. It is concluded from the analysis that the extent of preference for job training programmes is identified more with Markapur division (95.24 per cent) as compared to Ongole division (83.85 per cent)
2. It can be observed from the analysis that the extent of importance accorded to personal development in both Ongole division (20.77 per cent) Markapur division (35.24 per cent) to computer software compared to priorities given to management development in Markapur division (35.24 per cent) and leadership in Ongole division (23.08 per cent).
3. It is found from the analysis that majority of employees in both divisions opined that training is required for new employees.
4. Among total respondents, 85.71 per cent of Markapur division are satisfied with their present salary compared to Ongole division (76.92 per cent).

SUGGESTIONS

Based on the findings, the following suggestions are made to the management of the sample respondents to improve the efficiency of employees.

1. To improve the efficiency and update the knowledge of employees, the divisions should provide internal and external training programs according to the requirements.
2. Employee compensation or salary is an important factor which needs more attention. The mills should consider the nature of work and the rules and regulations relating to employees salary and wages.
3. Of all the aspects of human resource management practice followed, one of the main aspects is job satisfaction of employees. Once the employees are satisfied with their jobs, then they are satisfied with other aspects automatically. Hence, steps should be taken by the

management to satisfy the employees in their jobs by providing such an internal and external environment that ensures a healthy and happy workplace.

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